

POLYMER-BASED COMPOSITE NANOFIBRES FOR WOUND HEALING APPLICATIONS

V. Leung¹, R. Hartwell², H. Yang¹, E. Rahmani-Neishaboor², Y. Li², F. Ko^{1*}, A. Ghahary²

¹ Department of Materials Engineering, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada

² BC Professional Fire Fighters Burn & Wound Healing Lab., University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada

* Corresponding author (frank.ko@ubc.ca)

Keywords: *nanofibres, wound healing, burn treatment, electrospinning*

1 General Introduction

Materials play a significant role in defining functions for many products used today. Besides finding suitable materials for specific applications, the focus of materials engineers is to manipulate properties of given materials to suit these applications. Examples include microstructural engineering and materials alloying. Among those, the concept of combining desirable properties of different materials into composites has been used throughout time. The field has grown exponentially recently, with tremendous efforts towards developing composites for increasingly specialized applications such as armor protection, aviation, automotive, and energy. The attempt to utilize the full potential of composite materials is still ongoing, with more recent attempts in developing active composites, such as shape memory and heat regulating materials. Another class of application on which the composites community has been making progress is bioactive materials, with typical example being polymer composites for wound healing, which is greatly beneficial due to the intricate process involved.

Indeed, the wound care sector is one of the most advanced in biomedical industry, with a worldwide market worth of \$13 billion (2008) [1]. The massive demand on wound care comes from patients of both acute and chronic wounds. There are nearly 500,000 burn patients annually in the US requiring treatment [2], with 6 million patients in the US suffering from chronic wounds [3]. In addition, 120,000 surgical procedures, which create wounds, are performed daily. Advanced wound healing technologies are beneficial in reducing the burden on healthcare systems worldwide, which stems from the cost of medical care and loss of productivity linked

to the injuries. Autografting has remained the golden standard for treatment of major wounds. In addition, skin replacement products such as Integra and other injectable scaffolds have shown feasibility for partial and full-thickness wounds. However, improvements to current wound healing technology is required, as autografting suffers from donor site morbidity, artificial skins like Integra requires multiple surgical procedures, and injectable scaffolds lack mechanical integrity.

Electrospun nanofibres are recently introduced as mechanically robust scaffolds, and have been shown effective in tissue regeneration due to its large surface area to volume ratio, ease of fabrication, and capability as a drug encapsulation matrix [4]. In addition, previous work on nanofibres has demonstrated their superior cell regeneration compared to other forms such as gel and foam [4, 5]. Building on the success of these earlier studies, our goal is to develop nanofibre-based systems that can manage the different wound healing processes for different types of wounds. The complexity of the healing process and the dynamic nature of the body require composite materials to achieve multiple objectives associated with wound healing. Recently, the need for composite material designs in wound healing has been outlined in the work by Rahmani-Neishaboor et al. who produced a composite microsphere system containing poly(lactic-glycolic acid) (PLGA) and chitosan conjugated with stratafin [6], in which the chitosan provides drug binding ability and the PLGA provides protection against burst release of the drug. The work by Rahmani-Neishaboor et al. demonstrated that via composite designs, wound care products can become multifunctional. The focus of our study is therefore to manipulate properties of nanofibre wound dressings through composite designs in order

regulate the wound healing process while providing the necessary protection.

Our focus on wound healing management is on controlling the release rate of therapeutic elements, and scaffold mechanical properties. The specific target for release and mechanical properties depend on the type of wound and drugs considered. For example, a fresh wound may require a relatively quick release of antibiotics, whereas an epithelialized wound may require a more sustainable release of drugs for improving wound healing. Examples of release profiles for dressings for several types of wound are shown in **Figure 1**. It must be noted that in reality the optimal release profile depend greatly on the drug and patient condition, but the generalized profiles in **Figure 1** can nonetheless provide a starting objective for our study.

Figure 1: Examples of release profiles for different wounds (adopted from [7])

Materials play a significant role in both wound healing management and mechanical properties of the dressing. In our study, the importance of materials for wound healing is demonstrated by a composite scaffold containing electrospun polycaprolactone (PCL) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). A sandwich structured scaffold is considered, in which drug-loaded PVA is the protected by PCL outer shells in a layered organization. The drug release and mechanical properties of the composite, as well as methods for controlling these properties are assessed.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and Preparation

PCL and PVA, 98-99% hydrolyzed, was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Dichloromethane (DCM) and dimethylformamide (DMF), at a weight ratio of 1:1, were used to dissolve PCL (8 – 12 wt%) for the for the outer shell of the sandwich structured scaffold. All solvents in this study were purchased from Fisher Scientific. Distilled water was used to dissolve PVA (8 – 12 wt%) for the inner layer of the scaffold. Aqueous sodium tetraborate solutions were also prepared for crosslinking reactions with PVA.

2.2 Electrospinning

Polymer solutions were loaded into 10mL syringes with 20G1 needles (B-D). Electrospinning was performed using the Katotech nanofibre electrospinning unit at an applied voltage of 18 – 22 kV and a solution flow rate of 0.3 – 0.5 mL/hr. Nanofibres were collected on a stationary drum. Sandwich scaffold were prepared by first electrospinning a layer of PCL with thickness varying from 200 - 400 μ m, followed by a PVA layer and then a PCL layer of the same thickness as the first layer. In order to enhance the structural integrity of PVA fibres in aqueous environments, crosslinking was performed by spraying sodium tetraborate solutions onto the fibers after electrospinning of the PVA layer. It is also anticipated that crosslinking the PVA layer can further help control drug release from the fiber.

2.3 Optical Characterization

Nanofibre morphology was observed via a Hitachi S-3000N scanning electron microscope (SEM). The sandwich composite structure was observed in 3D using an Olympus LEXT 4000 laser confocal microscope. Images taken from SEM and confocal microscope were analyzed for fibre diameter, diameter distribution, and layer thickness using the software ImageJ.

2.4 Mechanical Characterization

Uniaxial tensile tests were performed on the composite nanofibres as well as nanofibres of individual polymers using a Katotech KES-G1 tensile tester with a strain rate of 0.1 cm/s. The average ultimate tensile strengths and strains were

calculated from an average of 10 tests on different specimens from each sample.

2.5 Drug Release

To demonstrate the drug release capability of the composite nanofibres, a model drug was obtained from the BC Professional Firefighters Burn and Wound Healing Laboratory, and was added to the PVA layer, such that the resultant nanofibre sandwich structure contained the drug in the middle layer. To measure drug release, scaffolds were incubated at 37°C in 1x phosphate buffered saline (PBS) solution at pH 7.5 for a specific length of time. 500 µL of PBS was taken from each sample and the drug released was measured spectrophotometrically by absorbance.

3 Results

3.1 Electrospinning and Crosslinking

Electrospun PCL and PVA showed uniform nanofibers with diameters ranging from 180 – 250 nm for PCL and 270 – 330 nm for PVA. After crosslinking the PVA layer with a sodium tetraborate solution mist, it was found that the PVA nanofibre layer partially gelled, resulting in reduced morphological uniformity. However, laser confocal image showed that the sandwich structure containing distinct layers of PCL and PVA remained after crosslinking, as seen in **Figure 2**. Two sandwich structured samples were electrospun in this study, with the only difference being the average thickness of PCL shells, which were 250 µm and 400 µm, respectively. The average PVA layer thickness was fixed at 250 µm to maintain a constant amount of loaded drugs.

Figure 2: Laser confocal image of the sandwich structured dressing containing drug-loaded PVA between PCL layers

3.2 Drug Release Management

The goal in wound healing management is to be able to control the release profile of therapeutic elements such as drugs and cell signaling molecules, thereby enabling development of quick, moderate, and slow release wound dressing systems. A quick release system may be suitable for antibiotics or for exudating wounds for which frequent change of dressing is desired, whereas a slow release system may be suitable for wounds for which frequent interruption is not desired.

Drug release from nanofibres involves several mechanisms, including liquid-state and solid-state diffusion, and matrix degradation. In liquid-state diffusion, body fluid swells the nanofibre, and transport drugs that are desorbed from the fibre surface to the surrounding wound. In solid-state diffusion, drugs trapped within fibres diffuse towards the surface and then released via penetrating liquid. Matrix degradation releases drug via disintegration of the drug carrier. Fine-tuning release profiles of wound dressings requires detailed manipulation of each mechanism. The effect of various electrospinning parameters on the release rate, as well as the relationship between drug release via diffusion and fibre area have been examined in several previous studies [8-10]. In our current study, drug release via liquid-state diffusion and

degradation is controlled by using a combination of the hydrophilic, quick-degrading PVA and hydrophobic, slow-degrading PCL. In addition, crosslinking of the PVA layer can further limit both liquid and solid state diffusion as well as matrix degradation, providing further control over the release profile.

It is clear that the wound dressing with the quickest release is one containing only drug-loaded PVA fibres, which swells easily and is highly hydrophilic. Indeed, our studies showed significant burst release, with all loaded drugs released within 30 minutes. For applications that require a more gradual drug release, we crosslinked the PVA fibres with sodium tetraborate, which decreases swelling and matrix degradation rate, and the release rate was reduced, with 90% of loaded drugs released after 3 hours. Further reduction of liquid-state diffusion was achieved by adding PCL protective layers of varying thicknesses. The release profiles in Figure 3 compare the sustainability of drug release between a crosslinked PVA electrospun layer (no PCL shell), and sandwich structured PCL-PVA-PCL composites with varying PCL thickness (250 and 400 μm thick PCL shells). Looking at the profile of the crosslinked PVA electrospun layer (no PCL shell), the effect of crosslinking on drug release can be observed, since it was mentioned earlier that without crosslinking, 100% of the drugs were released within 30 minutes. In addition, it was clear that drug release rate decreased as the thickness of the outer PCL layer increased. It is also evident from Figure 3 that with a combination of composite system and crosslinking, drug release from a PVA carrier is highly controllable and sustainable release can be achieved.

Figure 3: Release profile of model drug from PVA carrier with no shell, 250 μm and 400 μm thick PCL shells.

3.3 Mechanical Properties Control

While controlled drug release enables the wound dressing to actively manage the healing process, the mechanical properties of the dressing is also important because it must be sufficiently durable for handling and application. In terms of applications, the dressing must be able to withstand forces applied by tissue cells, which has been found in the past via culture force monitor (CFM) studies on fibroblasts to be in the order of 0.1 nN per cell [11-13]. In addition, the dressing must also withstand loads applied by the patient upon movements. For handling, unlike injectable scaffolds which are contained as a liquid, nanofibre dressings are handled as a textile and must therefore have corresponding durability. Figure 4 shows the uniaxial tensile properties of PCL and PVA (crosslinked and non-crosslinked) as well as composites of the two polymers. The sandwich structured composite displayed high ultimate tensile strength at low strains, typical of crosslinked PVA, and high ultimate strain, typical of PCL. It can also be seen that the tensile strength of the composite nanofibres are significantly higher than that of injectable scaffolds, which is in the order of 50 – 100 kPa [14]. Indeed, the tensile strength of the electrospun composite is in the same order as microfibrinous textile dressings such as Biofix and Resolut LT [15], indicating that the electrospun system can be handled like existing textile products.

Figure 4: Mechanical properties of PVA and PCL electrospun fibres, and their composite

4.0 Summary and Future Prospects

In this study we have developed a bioactive composite nanofibre system for wound healing. Through a combination of hydrophilic and hydrophobic materials, and crosslinking treatments, we have demonstrated control over the drug release from a PVA carrier. By changing the degree of PVA crosslinking and the thickness of a hydrophobic protective shell, we were able to vary the drug release profile to obtain systems with quick release as well as those with more gradual release. The drug release control enables us to develop dressings suitable for different drugs and for various types of wounds. The composite system and crosslinking technique also allowed manipulation of mechanical properties of the dressing which affects its handling and durability during application.

The future work in our study lies in further fine-tuning of therapeutic and mechanical performance of the dressing, with the ultimate goal of being able to tailor wound dressings such that it can effectively interact with specific wounds and effectively manage the healing process. In terms of drug release, further control can be achieved by careful manipulation of the release mechanisms. For example, using more hydrophobic polymers than PCL as the protective shell in a sandwich structured system can further extend the duration of drug

release, and previous studies have shown that release duration in the range of 2-3 months could be achieved [16, 17]. For mechanical properties, further control can be achieved via changing fibre orientation, crystallinity, and strengthening techniques such as annealing and nanoparticle reinforcement. The knowledge gained through these studies will then become the basis for the development of a new generation of wound dressings that can more appropriately address the socio-economic needs of the medical sector that was outlined at the beginning of this paper.

References

1. Research and Markets, *The Future of the Wound Care Management Market to 2015*. 2009.
2. American Burn Association. *Burn Incidence Fact Sheet*. 2009 January 20, 2010]; Available from: http://www.ameriburn.org/resources_factsheet.php.
3. de la Torre, J.I. and J.A. Chambers, *Wound Healing, Chronic Wounds*. Medscape Reference, 2008.
4. Leung, V. and F.K. Ko, *Biomedical Applications of Nanofibers*. *Polymers Advanced Technologies*, 2010. **22**(3): p. 350-365.
5. Leung, V., et al. *Alginate Nanofibre Based Tissue Engineering Scaffolds by Electrospinning*. in *Society for the Advancement of Materials and Process Engineering 2010 Conference*. 2010. Seattle, WA.
6. Rahman-Neishaboor, E., et al., *Composite Hydrogel Formulations of Stratafin to Control MMP-1 Expression in Dermal Fibroblasts*. *Pharmaceutical Research*, 2009. **26**(8): p. 2002-2014.
7. Ko, F., et al. *Bioactive Nanofibres for Wound Dressing Applications*. in *Textile Bioengineering and Informatics Society 2011 International Symposium*. 2011. Beijing, China.
8. Gandhi, M., et al., *Mechanistic Examination of Protein Release from Polymer Nanofibers*. *Molecular Pharmaceutics*, 2009. **6**(2): p. 641-647.

9. Katti, D.S., et al., *Bioresorbable Nanofiber-Based Systems for Wound Healing and Drug Delivery: Optimization of Fabrication Parameters*. Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part B: Applied Biomaterials, 2005. **70B**(2): p. 286-296.
10. Srikar, R., et al., *Desorption-Limited Mechanism of Release from Polymer Nanofibers*. Langmuir, 2008. **24**: p. 965-974.
11. Eastwood, M., D. McGrouther, and R. Brown, *Fibroblast responses to mechanical forces*. Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part H: Journal of Engineering in Medicine, 1998. **212**(2): p. 85-92.
12. Eastwood, M., et al., *Quantitative analysis of collagen gel contractile forces generated by dermal fibroblasts and the relationship to cell morphology*. Journal of Cellular Physiology, 1996. **166**(1): p. 33-42.
13. Zaleskas, J.M., et al., *Contractile forces generated by articular chondrocytes in collagen-glycosaminoglycan matrices*. Biomaterials, 2004. **25**(7-8): p. 1299-1308.
14. Hong, Y., et al., *Mechanical properties and in vivo behavior of a biodegradable synthetic polymer microfiber - extracellular matrix hydrogel biohybrid scaffold*. Biomaterials, 2011. **32**: p. 3387-3394.
15. Rho, K.S., et al., *Electrospinning of collagen nanofibers: Effects on the behavior of normal human keratinocytes and early-stage wound healing*. Biomaterials, 2006. **27**: p. 1452-1461.
16. Chew, S.Y., et al., *Sustained Release of Proteins from Electrospun Biodegradable Fibers*. Biomacromolecules, 2005. **6**(4): p. 2017-2024.
17. Saraf, A., et al., *Regulated non-viral gene delivery from coaxial electrospun fiber mesh scaffolds*. Journal of Controlled Release, 2010. **143**(1): p. 95-103.